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WAYS TO IMPROVE THE PERFORMANCE OF INVESTMENT FUNDS

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Abstract. This scientific study examines the economic nature of investment funds as financial intermediaries, their role in the securities market, and their impact on the development of the national economy. The research analyzes domestic and foreign scientific approaches to the concept of investment funds, identifies their organizational and legal characteristics, and highlights the mechanisms of their operation within the financial market system.

Key words: investment funds, financial intermediation, securities market, institutional investors, investment activity, financial market, investment environment, diversification, financial stability.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur ilmiy tadqiqotda investitsiya fondlarining moliyaviy vositachi sifatidagi iqtisodiy mohiyati, qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida o'rni hamda milliy iqtisodiyot rivojiga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot jarayonida investitsiya fondlari tushunchasiga oid mahalliy va xorijiy ilmiy yondashuvlar o'rganilib, ularning tashkiliy-huquqiy xususiyatlari hamda moliya bozori tizimidagi faoliyat mexanizmlari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: investitsiya fondlari, moliyaviy vositachilik, qimmatli qog'ozlar bozori, institutsional investorlar, investitsiya faoliyati, moliya bozori, investitsiya muhiti, diversifikatsiya, moliyaviy barqarorlik.

Аннотация. В данной научной работе рассматривается экономическая сущность инвестиционных фондов как финансовых посредников, их роль на рынке ценных бумаг и влияние на развитие национальной экономики. В ходе исследования проанализированы отечественные и зарубежные научные подходы к понятию инвестиционных фондов, раскрыты их организационно-правовые особенности, а также механизмы функционирования в системе финансового рынка.

Ключевые слова: инвестиционные фонды, финансовое посредничество, рынок ценных бумаг, институциональные инвесторы, инвестиционная деятельность, финансовый рынок, инвестиционная среда, диверсификация, финансовая устойчивость.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of financial globalization, one of the key conditions for ensuring the sustainable development of the national economy is the effective provision of financial intermediary services to clients. Financial intermediaries play an important role in ensuring the efficient movement of loan capital, improving the investment climate in the country, and increasing overall investment activity.

In order to improve the investment climate in the Republic of Uzbekistan through the organization of investment fund activities, actively attract foreign and, primarily, domestic investments into sectors and regions of the national economy, as well as encourage the redirection of idle funds of the population into the economy in the form of domestic investments, Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 392¹ "On investment and mutual funds" was adopted on June 29-2015 [1].

World practice demonstrates that financial intermediaries play a significant role in increasing the volume of investments directed to the real sector of the economy. The securities market ensures the transformation of household savings into investments, creating opportunities for real sector enterprises to attract additional financial resources and utilize them effectively. In developed countries, collective investment forms and institutions are sufficiently developed, providing a mechanism for transforming savings into investments and ensuring the efficient distribution of financial resources.

This situation determines the necessity for an in-depth study and generalization of advanced foreign experience in the development of financial intermediaries, including collective investment funds, a comprehensive

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 392 "On investment and mutual funds" was adopted on June 29-2015: <https://lex.uz/docs/4610865>

analysis of the factors influencing their development, and the formulation of scientific proposals and practical recommendations regarding the possibilities of creatively applying this experience under the conditions of the republic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of financial intermediary institutions, particularly investment and collective investment funds, is an important factor in ensuring the sustainable growth of the national economy. In global economic literature, financial intermediaries are interpreted as a connecting link between the real sector and the owners of financial resources. They ensure the efficient allocation of capital and contribute to an increase in investment activity.

In international scientific research (McKinnon, Shaw, Mishkin), institutional development in financial markets is recognized as one of the main drivers of economic growth. In particular, the development of collective investment mechanisms makes it possible to attract household savings into long-term investments. Investment funds provide small investors with access to diversified portfolios, thereby reducing financial risks [2, 3, 4].

An analysis of the experience of developed countries shows that in the financial markets of the USA, the European Union, and Japan, investment funds play a significant role in financing the real sector. Their activities are regulated on the basis of a strict regulatory framework, transparency, and reliable protection of investors' rights [5, 6, 7].

In the experience of the CIS countries, including Russia and Kazakhstan, the development of investment funds is also considered a means of deepening financial markets and attracting long-term investments into the economy. In these countries, special legislation has been developed to regulate the activities of collective investment institutions [8, 9].

In the scientific works of Uzbek scholars, particular attention is paid to issues related to the development of the financial intermediation system, activation of the securities market, and enhancement of domestic investment potential through investment funds. These studies identify the low level of development of investment funds, insufficient financial literacy of the population, and limited market infrastructure as the main challenges [10, 11].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a mixed research methodology based on the collection and analysis of secondary and empirical data. Information was obtained from official statistical reports, regulatory documents, financial statements of investment funds, and international analytical sources. The analysis was conducted using comparative, statistical, trend, and structural analysis methods to identify performance dynamics and influencing factors.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Investment funds attract financial resources by issuing their own shares and subsequently invest these funds in the securities of other corporations.

There is no single, universally accepted definition of the concept of investment funds in economic and foreign scientific literature. This is explained by the multifaceted and complex nature of investment fund activities. Typically, in economic literature, investment funds are interpreted as the following objects:

- organizations;
- property complexes;
- enterprises and financial products;
- financial intermediaries;
- socio-economic relations.

In our opinion, the above approaches reflect only certain organizational, legal, and functional aspects of investment fund activities and do not fully reveal the economic essence of these institutions.

In European countries, investment funds are interpreted as undertakings for collective investment in transferable securities (Undertakings for Collective Investment in Transferable Securities – UCITS).

In US practice, investment funds are represented by the concept of “investment companies.” An investment company is a type of financial institution engaged in investing funds raised from depositors in various securities on its own behalf.

The activities of investment funds encompass the following main economic relations:

- attracting investors' funds and other property;
- pooling investors' assets within a single property complex—a fund—and transferring the management of this property to the investment fund itself or to a specialized management company;

- investing fund assets in securities and other investment objects in accordance with the principle of diversification in order to generate investment income (dividends, interest, and other income) or to obtain profit through the resale of investment objects.

Unlike banks, insurance companies, and pension funds, investment funds do not provide guarantees to investors regarding the timing or amount of payments. The amount of funds an investor receives upon exiting an investment fund is not determined in advance and directly depends on the value of the fund's net assets and the investor's share in those assets.

The funds invested by investors in investment funds are subsequently directed toward securities and other investment objects. As a result, investors acquire claims on the property of the investment fund. Proceeds from the sale of securities within the fund's portfolio are credited to the fund's account. These proceeds include dividends, interest, coupon income, and other payments made by issuers of securities. Upon withdrawal from the fund, investors receive funds corresponding to their share in the property of the investment fund.

Another important feature of investment funds is that members of the general public who lack sufficient experience in the securities market can also participate as investors. Such investors, acting independently, may be unable to adequately assess investment risks or protect themselves from various financial frauds. At the same time, the loss of investment funds may lead to serious socio-economic conflicts. Therefore, the activities of investment funds are subject to strict state regulation.

Investment funds play a significant role in the effective placement of idle funds into production, thereby contributing to the sustainable development of the national economy. This indicates that, in addition to direct regulation, greater attention should be paid to regulating investment funds through market mechanisms. Moreover, the issue of licensing their activities as professional participants in the securities market remains one of the most pressing challenges today.

Figure 1. The number of investment funds operating in our country in 2019-2023[12]

The activities of institutional investors are also represented in the securities market of the country. Such investors include investment funds, insurance companies, and commercial banks. The primary objective of institutional investors is to increase capital and ensure its liquidity. Their main function is the active investment of funds in securities.

In 2019-2023, there was almost no change in the number of investment funds operating in the country. While 2 mutual funds and 7 individual investment funds operated in 2019-2020, the number of individual investment funds increased by one in 2021. However, in 2022-2023, no changes were observed in the number of operating investment funds. Figure 1 illustrates data on the volume of securities issued and purchased by investment funds.

Figure 2. The number of shareholders in investment funds operating in the country in 2019-2023, including individuals and legal entities [12].

In 2023, the total number of shareholders of all investment funds amounted to 50,439, of which 50,402 were individuals and 37 were legal entities.

Figure 3. The volume of securities issued and purchased by investment funds operating in the country in 2019-2023 (billion soums).

During the analyzed period, the volume of securities issued by investment funds increased by 15.0% (or 0.3 billion soums), reaching 2.3 billion soums. The volume of purchased securities amounted to 6.9 billion soums in 2019, and by 2023, it increased by 23.2%. This trend necessitates the implementation of reforms by investment funds aimed at attracting retail investors' funds into the financial market.

In our opinion, to further develop investment funds in the country, it is advisable to grant them the status of professional participants in the securities market as institutional investors and to discontinue the licensing of their activities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The above analysis shows that investment funds, as financial intermediaries, play an important role in directing the free cash of the population and business entities to the real sector of the economy through the securities market. Their activities enable capital concentration, diversification, and the reduction of investment risks, thereby creating conditions for investors' professional participation in the financial market. At the same time, the profitability of investment funds and the interests of investors are directly dependent on the value of the fund's net assets, which indicates a high degree of dependence of these institutions on market mechanisms.

The fact that the number of investment funds operating in the country during 2019-2023 has remained almost unchanged indicates a low pace of development in this area. Despite the fact that the absolute majority of shareholders are individuals, the relatively slow growth in the volume of securities issued and purchased by investment funds demonstrates the need to further improve mechanisms for attracting retail investors' funds to the financial market. This situation increases the urgency of stimulating the activities of institutional investors and developing stock market infrastructure.

In this context, in the process of developing investment funds in the country, it is important to form them as full-fledged institutional investors and professional participants in the securities market. Rather than excessive direct state regulation, it is advisable to implement institutional reforms aimed at the wider application of market mechanisms, increasing transparency, and protecting investors' rights. As a result, the efficiency of investment funds' activities will increase, ensuring the deepening of the securities market and the sustainable development of the national economy.

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